

Studies on consolute solutions of two immiscible conjugated solvent systems with halide salts and carboxylic acids

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The water-phenol consolute solutions have been subjected to mutual solubility temperature (MST) and composition (MSC) studies with a fixed amount of halide salt and carboxylic acid additives. From the polynomial fit of temperature and composition data, the upper consolute solution temperature (UCST) and the corresponding consolute composition (CSC) values are obtained. The UCST and CSC behavior have been considered as the function of size of cation and anion of salt, and basicity and methylene groups of acid molecules. The UCST and CSC values demonstrate the state of hydration of ions, and ion-water and hydrophilic interactions of acids. The sizes of ions are found to affect the water structure through structure-breaking action. Ion-hydrated complexes are formed which result in well organized ion-water structure which make homogeneous phase at higher temperature. AlCl_3 , CaCl_2 and FeCl_3 salts are reported with higher UCST values and FeCl_3 is found with two UCST and CSCs. The acids are found to produce comparatively lower UCST than those of salts.

Hydration of ions of various sizes with partial molar volume and XRD technique in homogeneous mixed solvents at ordinary temperatures are useful for ion-water interactions¹. While the studies in homogeneous solution of two immiscible phases at higher temperatures are of interest, the interactions of ions and carboxylic acids in water-phenol homogeneous single phase are studied. The solutions are of industrial significance but the restricted mutual solubility of water and phenol reduces the applications². Therefore, extensive studies to enhance the solubility³ with mono- (NaF, NaCl, NaBr, NaI, KCl, RbCl, KBr, KI), di- (MgCl_2 , CaF_2 , CaCl_2 , SrCl_2) and trivalent (AlCl_3 , CrCl_3 , FeCl_3) series of salts and mono- (formic), di- (oxalic, malonic, succinic) and tribasic (citric acid) acids are made. The two series of sodium and potassium monovalent salts are chosen for studies. The studies are designed to clearly understand the effect on the upper consolute solution temperature (UCST) and composition (CSC) of phenol, aiming to prepare the homogeneous solution of two immiscible phases with suitable additives as the solutions find applications for understanding of thermochemical behavior of colloidal and disinfectant solutions.

Results and discussion

Mutual solubility temperature (MST) for each composition of consolute solution with additive was determined and plotted against MSC. Figs. 1 and 2 represent the effect of addition of tribasic salts, and oxalic, malonic, succinic and citric acids. UCST and CSC data obtained from their apex, are given in Table 1.

UCST and CSC values of water-phenol system with $\pm 0.15^\circ$ and $\pm 0.35\%$ standard error, show close agreement with those of literature⁴ and are considered as reference for additives. The values for pure water + phenol system are considered as reference data for the additives. Salts and acids reorient water structure through ion-dipole and hydrophilic interactions resulting in a considerable variation in UCST and CSC values. The interactions involve the hydration of ions by monomers of water which intensifies aqueous phase by repelling out or salt out phenol from aqueous phase mutually⁵. The order of UCST values for monovalent salts is noted as $\text{NaI} > \text{NaBr} > \text{RbCl} > \text{KI} > \text{KCl} > \text{KBr} > \text{NaF} > \text{NaCl}$, and CSC as $\text{NaI} > \text{NaBr} > \text{NaCl} > \text{NaF} > \text{KI} > \text{KBr} > \text{KCl} > \text{RbCl}$. This indicates a stronger interaction of Na^+ in association of I^- , Br^- and water (ion-dipole) hydration interactions in series by holding water molecules to the integrated phase of water. Induced dipole moment in case of I^- and Br^- due to their larger size increases the water-phenol mutual solubility resulting in higher CSC in series but interactions of Na^+ in association of F^- and Cl^- are weaker than other members of the series as the more electronegative F and Cl attract the electron pair. This may consume electronic energy of the salt partially. This trend of Na^+ proves a lower hydration of Na^+ in association with smaller halide ions and polarization of bigger ions do strengthen anion-water interactions that need higher thermal energy to break the ion-hydrated water to get free for mutual mixing. It may be concluded that larger anion-water comparatively causes stronger interactions. Hydration interactions both of cations and anions drive water away from phenol phase

where mixing of this state requires higher thermal energy that increases the UCST. Similar explanations are true for other members of the series. The order of UCST values of halide anions of sodium salt is $\text{NaI} > \text{NaBr} > \text{NaF} > \text{NaCl}$ and CSC is $\text{NaI} > \text{NaBr} > \text{NaCl} > \text{NaF}$. The trend proves the greater contribution of polarization⁶ on I^- and Br^- and effective nuclear charge on F^- and Cl^- for integrating an aqueous phase and mutual mixing needs higher thermal energy thus raising UCST. Larger CSC values predict that the polarization of Br^- and I^- may cause induced dipole in phenol phase that increases mutual dissolution. The second series of monovalent salts show UCST as $\text{RbCl} > \text{KI} > \text{KCl} > \text{KBr}$, and CSC as $\text{KI} > \text{KBr} > \text{KCl} > \text{RbCl}$. Here the trend proves a shifting of bonded electron pair of RbCl molecule towards a smaller and more electronegative Cl from the larger Rb and on dissociation both the ions take part in ion-solvation interactions. The order of UCST values is $\text{KCl} > \text{NaCl}$, $\text{NaBr} > \text{KBr}$, $\text{NaI} > \text{KI}$, and of CSC is $\text{NaCl} > \text{KCl}$, $\text{NaBr} > \text{KBr}$ and $\text{NaI} > \text{KI}$. The trends are according to the size of cation and anions, e.g. KCl with higher polarization causes greater hydration resulting in higher UCST than that of NaCl . Probably $4s^1$ electron of K is responsible for this trend. While the least CSC for RbCl in the series indicates less water structure-breaking from hydrated complex. The UCST and CSC values for the divalent chloride salts are $\text{CaCl}_2 > \text{SrCl}_2 > \text{MgCl}_2 > \text{CaF}_2$ with same trend for CSC. The trend indicates shifting of CaCl_2 bonded electron pair towards Cl , due to greater electronegativity and the same is true for larger Sr ion. But with MgCl_2 , the nuclear charge of

Mg and Ca balances the electronegativity of Cl and F and is responsible for the observed trend.

In general, the order of values of UCST for trivalent salts is found as $\text{FeCl}_3 > \text{AlCl}_3 > \text{CrCl}_3$, and CSC as $\text{AlCl}_3 > \text{FeCl}_3 > \text{CrCl}_3$. Here Fe^{3+} , Al^{3+} and Cr^{3+} are effective to interact with water. The fully half-filled $3d$ and vacant $4s$ of Fe^{3+} may form complex molecule with water as neutral ligand, and this seems to be responsible for UCST trend in the series. While small size of Al^{3+} causes greater hydration than Cr^{3+} , perhaps the incompletely half filled $3d$ shell comparatively does not seem effective for ion-hydration interactions for Cr in the series, FeCl_3 was noted with two UCST and CSCs (Table 1). The first set of UCST and CSC

Table 1. The upper consolute solution temperature (UCST) and consolute solution composition (CSC) of phenol for 0.1 mol kg^{-1} salt and carboxylic acid aqueous solution except 0.01 mol kg^{-1} CrCl_3 and CaF_2 due to solubility restriction in water

Additive	UCST in °C	CSC in weight	N data points
Water-phenol pure	65.63	36.300	21
Monovalent			
NaF ($\text{Na} = 3s^1$)	71.00	33.414	15
NaCl	68.00	38.460	09
NaBr	75.65	44.348	17
NaI	76.44	45.480	12
KCl ($\text{K} = 4s^1$)	72.40	22.920	09
RbCl ($\text{Rb} = 5s^1$)			
KBr	72.00	32.952	17
KI	73.02	33.048	13
Divalent			
MgCl_2 ($\text{Mg} = 3s^2$)	75.15	44.310	16
CaF_2 ($\text{Ca} = 4s^2$)	66.50	26.658	16
CaCl_2 ($\text{Ca} = 4s^2$)	89.45	66.660	13
SrCl_2 ($\text{Sr} = 5s^2 4p^6$)	81.25	55.299	16
Trivalent salt			
AlCl_3 ($\text{Al} = 3s^2 3p^1$)	84.60	56.907	31
CrCl_3 ($\text{Cr} = 4s^1 3d^5$)	67.65	39.863	15
FeCl_3 ($\text{Fe} = 4s^2 3d^6$)	98.75	43.507	21
FeCl_3 (second UCST)	97.50	19.319	21
Monobasic			
Formic acid	65.60	33.391	16
Acetic acid	65.12	34.598	12
Dibasic			
Oxalic acid	74.00	55.550	09
Malonic acid	71.55	56.878	12
Succinic acid	62.00	44.391	14
Tribasic acid			
Citric acid	65.35	33.195	17

Fig. 1. Y-axis : Upper consolute solution temperature in °C, and X-axis : consolute composition of phenol in weight percent : (O) water-phenol, (●) AlCl_3 , (▲) FeCl_3 , (Δ) CrCl_3 .

values is higher (Fig. 1) and the second CSC is found to be the least among the chosen additives.

In case of monobasic acids, UCST of formic > acetic acid, while CSC of acetic acid > formic. In case of dibasic acids, the values of UCST are oxalic > malonic > succinic acid, and of CSC are malonic > oxalic > succinic acid. The trends indicate that the carboxylic group causes stronger hydrophilic interactions and methylene group reduces the UCST by developing hydrophobic interactions with phenol that decrease the interfacial potential⁷ of water and phenol phases leading to an increase mutual solubility. Therefore, a greater basicity with zero or minimum number of $-CH_2-$ in acid molecule proves greater acid-water interactions.

The order of UCST values with acids is oxalic > malonic > formic > citric > acetic > succinic, and that of CSC is malonic > oxalic > succinic > acetic > formic > citric (Fig. 2). The trend proves greater hydrophilic interactions of carboxylic and hydroxyl groups of citric acid. While methylene groups of succinic and citric acids make hydrophobic interaction⁸ (Table 1). The observed UCST and CSC values for formic and oxalic acids without $-CH_2-$ indicate greater hydrophilic interactions⁹ and the $-CH_2-$ groups of citric acid establish a greater structuredness of water¹⁰ due to hydrophobic interactions. In comparison to the categories of salts, the acids are reported with lower UCST and average CSC values (Table 1). This effect is attributed to the decrease of interfacial potential^{7,11} of wa-

ter and phenol phases due to hydrophilic interactions of carboxylic group and hydrophobic interaction of methylene group.

Experimental

0.1 mol kg⁻¹ of each salt and acid solution in water (w/w) was prepared separately. Due to solubility limitation, 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ CaF₂ and CrCl₃ aqueous solutions were used. The individual binary aqueous solution + phenol in 2 : 8 ratio was taken in the sample tube of borosil glass (150 × 15 mm dia). The tube was mounted on a steel-stand placed in paraffin oil filled in the thermostat ($\pm 0.01^\circ$) and stirred. The disappearance of water and phenol immiscible phases on heating and reappearance on switching off the heating (air-cooling) was viewed through a cathetometer placed at a distance of 1m from bath, and the temperatures for both were noted.

Phenol and additives (A.R., B.D.H.) were used as received. Demineralized, triple-distilled (with KOH and KMnO₄) and degassed water was used.

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Fig. 2. Y-axis : Upper consolute solution temperature in $^\circ\text{C}$, and X-axis : consolute composition of phenol in weight percent : (O) oxalic, (●) malonic, (Δ) succinic, (\blacktriangle) citric acid.